

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
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DUQUE'S TAX REFORM IN COLOMBIA: "A TRAGEDY FORETOLD"

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POLICY STATEMENT

In early April 2021, Colombian President Iván Duque announced a tax reform project aimed at raising 23 billion Colombian pesos (US\$6.3 billion) to deal with the crisis generated by the new coronavirus pandemic, expanding the solidarity income program. The measure foresees to increase the collection base with the collection of IVA (added value tax) of 19% on the rates of essential public services, which would directly affect the lower and middle classes of society. Realizing the possibility of raising taxes, which went against one of the promises of a tax reduction campaign, a series of rallies broke out across the country against the project at the end of April. After four days of uninterrupted protests, President Duque decided to remove it from Parliament. Despite the measure and the purpose of demonstrations supposedly being achieved at that time, protests continued, and the profile of participants changed. The violence increased, with the consequent increase in deaths and injuries among protesters and police officers.

BACKGROUND

The antecedents of the current protests can be found in 2018, when several student mobilizations demanded government attention to education, especially higher education. Then came the large protests of 2019 called by the *Comité Nacional del Paro* (National Committee of Strike), representing Colombian youth.

The lack of progress on the points of the 2016 peace agreement and the series of assassinations of social leaders linked to different agendas were some of the critical issues for triggering these demonstrations.

At the time, president Duque government volunteered to address the matter by calling the *Conversación Nacional* (national conversations), which had no concrete results, culminating in the great strike of November 21, 2019. The pandemic and quarantine policies dampened the momentum of the demonstrations.

However, the announcement of Duque's tax reform amid the devastating consequences of the pandemic, including the economic crisis, was the last straw for the reactivation and resurgence of protests in various parts of Colombian territory. Protests now demand, more specifically: a more egalitarian economy, new reforms of the National Police, and the country's health system.

Despite the drop in poverty rates in the country since 2002, Colombia still has one of the highest rates of social inequality in Latin America.

FINDINGS

- (1) Concomitantly with the various allegations of human rights violations by the country's police forces, the Colombian government claimed that as of May 1, with the arrival of buses from the interior, the protests were merely led by groups of guerrilla dissidents from the FARC and the ELN. The claim seems exaggerated at first, but the possibility of infiltration is not ruled out. Since May, former Colombian President Andrés Pastrana (1998-2002) warned that the Venezuelan government is infiltrating protests in Colombia. In addition, a commission coming from Argentina, supposedly as a human rights observer, also suffered accusations of attempts to destabilize the Colombian government after leaked audios of a meeting of them talking of the removal of President Iván Duque.
- (2) From a strategic point of view, the Colombian left follows the path of demonstrations in Chile in October 2019, whose protests started due to the increase in the price of transport controlled by the government, which, even after retreating, saw the population continue to protest in the streets. After the successful experience in Chile and the forthcoming elections in Colombia, which will take place in May 2022, the Colombian left takes advantage of and foments the wave of protests to destabilize the Duque government and earn electoral dividends depending on how much this one will yield.
- (3) President Duque's lack of leadership is evident, in the first place, due to the lack of political experience; secondly, due to the unpredictable circumstance arising from the new coronavirus pandemic.
- (4) Despite being a successor to Álvaro Uribe, elected under the ex-president's campaign, although keeping to the right in the political spectrum, Duque did not play the role that was expected of him as President, nor did he migrate to more popular policies, in theory, from the leftmost spectrum. With the economic consequences of the measures to contain the pandemic, Duque chose to implement and increase social programs, deciding to do so via tax increases, contradicting himself. So he achieved something exotic: uniting two political spectrums in a common cause, a cause that, despite facing the right and liberals, coming from a right-wing government, also managed to bring together left-wing leaders.

CONCLUSIONS

- It is a fact that public forces have abused their authority in the protests. It remains to be seen whether the human rights violations and the murders of which the Colombian police forces are accused are systematic conduct of the state or specific to some of its members
 - There is a lack of "Virtú et Fortuna": there is a lack of leadership demonstrated in the little political experience and government negotiations, which is added to the lack of luck due to the presence of covid19.
 - Concerning the political issue, the Colombian elections that will take place in May 2022 are already taking over the Colombian political environment, making electoral speeches overlap with coherent analyzes of the situation and effective political practice. Recent surveys, in the heat of events carried out by the Latin American Strategic Center for Geopolitics (CELAG), indicate that more than half of those interviewed believe in the possibility that Gustavo Petro, the greatest exponent of the left in

the country will be the next President.

- Concerning the economy, the trend is to be a more significant recession than the one caused by the consequences of the pandemic. Although the current 15.1% unemployment rate has dropped 4.7 percentage points from the same time in 2020, the unemployment rates are still alarming. And with the strike, more than 92% of foreign trade companies lost income.
- The Colombian government will continue to use the monopoly of force as a guarantee of security for the population against violent protests, and the Colombian population must demand serious and practical investigations into human rights violations.
- The *Comité Nacional del Paro* will continue to press and expand the agenda of demands supported by the left, with a view to the 2022 presidential elections.

SUGGESTIONS

- The Colombian government needs to be assertive in negotiations with the *Comité Nacional del Paro* and other groups claiming rights amid chaos, knowing how to balance the attacks of the security forces with the talks.
- urges that members of the police force involved in criminal actions against citizens be appropriately investigated and punished.
- urges that there be a prior intelligence effort to identify criminal groups infiltrated in the demonstrations, which threaten the lives of protesters in good faith, discredit the public security forces and destabilize the Colombian political environment.

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